

HEAT TRANSFER SIMULATION OF RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING BY THE FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

by

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ABSTRACT

In resin transfer molding (RTM) a stack of fiber mats or woven rovings is laid in the mold cavity. Then the mold is sealed and resin is injected. The mold and the resin can be heated in order to accelerate, by diminishing the viscosity of the resin, the filling of the mold. Proper care must be given so that polymerization is not initiated before the mold is completely filled. Therefore it is necessary to analyze the heat transfer phenomenon so as to control the temperature of the resin during the filling process. The heat equation contains convective terms that require special attention if a stable numerical scheme is to be obtained. The purpose of this paper is to describe the Taylor-Galerkin numerical method used to solve the heat equation as the mold fills up and to present some examples of simulations for three-dimensional parts.

Keywords: Resin Transfer Molding, finite elements, heat transfer

1. INTRODUCTION

Thermoset polymeric composites with continuous fiber reinforcements can be produced by injection of reactive liquids into molds with preplaced fiber mats. One process used increasingly in industry is Resin Transfer Molding (RTM). In this process, the resin streams are mixed by mechanical means and then injected into the mold containing stacks of fiber mats. A schematical view of the RTM process is given in Figure 1. Currently, most of the commercial products manufactured by RTM are developed based on the molder's experience and involve repeated experiments. In order to optimize the process and reduce its cost, a correct knowledge of mold filling becomes highly necessary.

In the RTM process, a stack of fiber mats or woven rovings is preplaced in the mold cavity, then the mold is sealed and resin is injected. The resin and the mold can be heated before injection in order to accelerate mold filling by diminishing the viscosity of the resin. However, proper care must be given so that resin polymerization is not initiated before the mold is completely filled. As a result, it is necessary to analyze the heat transfer phenomenon in order to control the temperature distribution of the resin during the filling process.

Recently, some investigations of non-isothermal resin flow through fiber mats were reported [1-2]. The key issue in non-isothermal mold filling concerns the resin flow through the preform and the heat transfer phenomenon occurring between the resin and the fiber reinforcement. If the resin flow has already been simulated by various numerical techniques, little work is available in the literature on the heat transfer itself. Gonzalez [1] proposed to study a simple one-dimensional thin cavity problem. Lin and al. [2] considered a two-dimensional model for the analysis of non-isothermal mold filling in cavities. They used local thermal equilibrium to simplify the energy equations.

Figure 1. Schematics of the RTM process.

In this paper, a two-dimensional model based on finite elements is presented to simulate non-isothermal mold filling for the RTM process. The Taylor-Galerkin method is used to avoid numerical instability due to the convective terms in the heat equation. In order to calculate the velocity of the resin flow at each time step, the heat transfer model is combined with the mold filling simulation based on non-conforming finite elements [3-5].

In the mold filling model, the impregnation of a fibrous preform is modeled as a flow in porous medium. It is governed by Darcy's law which states that the flow rate through an unit area is proportional to the pressure gradient. Using the velocity distribution computed by Darcy's law, a newly saturated domain is obtained at each time step upon which the heat transfer calculations are performed. The relationship between the two program modules is illustrated in Figure 2. In this paper, the emphasis is put on the heat transfer analysis. Some examples are presented in order to demonstrate the feasibility of the model.

Figure 2. Structure of the non-isothermal mold filling model.

2. MATHEMATICAL MODEL

Some assumptions are necessary to simplify the simulation. The heat transfer process is assumed to be in local thermal equilibrium, i.e., the temperature is the same at a local position for both the resin and the fiber mats, so that only one equation is needed to describe the temperature distribution. Radiation effects are neglected and no polymerization occurs during mold filling. With the above assumptions, the equations describing the mold filling and the heat transfer models can be written as follows:

a) Filling

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{V} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\vec{V} = - \frac{[k]}{\mu} \nabla P \quad (2)$$

where \vec{V} is the velocity vector, P the pressure, μ the resin viscosity and $[k]$ the permeability tensor for anisotropic porous media:

$$[k] = \begin{bmatrix} k_{xx} & k_{xy} \\ k_{yx} & k_{yy} \end{bmatrix}$$

b) Heat transfer equation

$$\rho C_p \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \vec{V} \cdot \nabla T \right) = k \Delta T \quad (3)$$

where T is the temperature of a reference unit volume of resin and the following thermal parameters are defined in a porous medium by (see ref. [2]):

$$\begin{aligned} \rho &= (\rho_r \rho_f) / (\rho_r W_r + \rho_f W_f) \\ C_p &= W_r C_{pr} + W_f C_{pf} \\ k &= (k_r k_f) / (k_r W_f + k_f W_r) \\ W_r &= \frac{\phi}{\rho_r} / \left(\frac{\phi}{\rho_r} + \frac{1-\phi}{\rho_f} \right) \\ W_f &= 1 - W_r \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where

W_r, W_f	:	weight fraction coefficient of resin, of fibers
Φ	:	porosity of the preform
ρ_r, ρ_f	:	resin density, fiber density
C_{pr}, C_{pf}	:	specific heat of the resin, of fibers
k_{pr}, k_{pf}	:	thermal conductivity of the resin, of fibers

The following boundary and initial conditions are considered for solving the heat equation (3):

a) Initial condition

$$T = T_o \text{ (temperature of the mold)}$$

b) Boundary conditions

at the injection gate:	$T _{\text{gate}} = T_{ro}$ (temperature of injected resin)
on the flow front:	$T _{\text{front}} = T_{fo}$ (temperature of the preform)

The interaction between the mold filling and heat transfer calculations is complex: (1) The resin viscosity is a function of temperature and (2) the geometry of the resin saturated domain changes during the filling process. So the two analysis are decoupled and performed successively at each time step.

3. FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

The numerical procedure used to simulate the filling process is based on a non-conforming finite element approximation of the pressure field, i.e., the pressure is continuous only at the middle nodes along the inter-element boundaries (see Figure 3). The advantage for using this kind of elements is to ensure the exact conservation of the resin flow rate across adjacent elements. This is indeed an important physical condition to be respected by a filling simulation model.

The pressure distribution is obtained by solving Darcy's law (2) and the continuity equation (1) at each time step inside the saturated domain. The velocity corresponding to the calculated pressure field is then used to determine the new position of the resin front. In order to follow the displacement of the resin front, a fill factor representing the filling level is associated to each element of the mesh. This technique is

Figure 3. Example of non-conforming finite element basis function.

widely used for simulations involving a moving front. A detailed presentation of the finite element formulation used for mold filling can be found in [3-5].

The heat transfer model is based on the same triangular element, but the temperature is linearly approximated at the three vertex nodes (see Figure 4). This approximation was chosen because:

- i) it provides a good stability for solving the transport-diffusion equation (3);
- ii) the computational cost is largely lower than for a non-conforming approximation in a triangular element. (It is evident that the number of vertex nodes is less than that of the middle nodes in a finite element mesh.)

As for all transport diffusion problems when convective terms become important, numerical oscillations tend to perturbate the temperature distribution obtained by a classical Galerkin scheme. Jean Donea developed the so-called Taylor-Galerkin procedure to avoid this problem [6]. He proposed to use a second order Taylor series for temporal discretization instead of the first order as in classical Galerkin schemes. Many research works applying this Taylor-Galerkin approach have demonstrated a good numerical stability as well as an easy implementation for transport-diffusion problems [7,8]. In our study, the Taylor-Galerkin method is employed to improve the numerical stability, especially in the case of important convective situations.

Figure 4. Triangular element for the heat transfer model.

If A denotes the total area of the mold and Γ the mold boundary, the classical variational formulation can be written as:

$$w_c = \int_A [\Psi \rho C_p (T^{t+\Delta t} - T^t + \Delta t \vec{V} \cdot \nabla T) - \Delta t (\Psi_x k T_x + \Psi_y k T_y)] dA + \int_{\Gamma} \Delta t k \frac{\partial T}{\partial n} dl \tag{5}$$

The Taylor-Galerkin scheme used in the heat transfer model takes the following expression:

$$w_{TG} = w_c [expression (5)] + \int_A \frac{\Delta t}{2} (\vec{V} \cdot \nabla \Psi) (\vec{V} \cdot \nabla T) dA \tag{6}$$

where Ψ in expressions (5) and (6) is a ponderation function. Relation (6) when discretized by the finite element method leads to a very stable numerical scheme for convection-conduction problems.

A numerical example will be presented in the next section to illustrate the stability of the Taylor-Galerkin scheme.

4. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

A numerical example is being considered here to demonstrate the capabilities of the non-isothermal filling model. A schematical view of the problem is shown in Figure 5. A hot polymer is injected in a rectangular mold with preplaced glass fibers. The temperature at the injection gate is imposed at 100°C and an ambient temperature of 20°C is assumed inside the mold..

Numerical results relating mold filling with the temperature distribution are presented in Figures 6-8. A relatively fine mesh is used to carry out the simulation (see Figure 6) in order to obtain a good precision of the resin front progression. The region near the injection gate is refined to assure a correct initialization of the simulation.

The progression of the resin front is shown in Figure 7. The shape of the resin front changes from a curve to a straight line during the filling. This was verified by experiments performed in our group. A good agreement between numerical and experimental fronts can be observed in the same figure. The temperature distribution at the end of the mold filling is shown in Figure 8. Note that a good stability for the solution of the heat equation was achieved. An elliptical form is expected because the heat transfer is mainly realized by the resin flow during the filling process and the main flow occurs in direction of the resin front progression, i.e., along the length of the mold.

5. CONCLUSION

A heat transfer simulation module integrated with a non-isothermal filling model is presented in this paper. The Taylor-Galerkin method used in the finite element model permits to guaranty a good stability of the temperature calculation when convection terms become dominant. A complete example with the filling simulation and the temperature calculation was presented. Further investigations will incorporate in the model simulation of the resin polymerization which is an important aspect of the RTM process.

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Figure 5. Geometry of the model problem.

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Figure 6. Mesh used for the non-isothermal mold filling simulation.

Figure 7. Comparison of experimental and numerical resin front positions.

Figure 8. Temperature distribution at the end of mold filling.